

**PARTICIPATION EXPECTATIONS FROM THE ELDERLY
PERSPECTIVE PARTICIPANTS OF THE COEXISTENCE SERVICE
AND COEXISTENCE STRENGTHENING , DURING THE PERIOD OF THE
PANDEMIC AND REMOTE WORK**

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to analyze the expectations of the elderly women assisted by the Service for Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds of the Reference Center for Social Assistance, in Vila Operária in the City of Paranavaí/PR. An experience report was used as a methodology, in view of the remote work implemented after the beginning of the world pandemic of Covid 19, in the year 2020. The Whatsapp tool was used for the development of activities and collection of information. It is concluded that the elderly participants in the research showed signs of social vulnerability, which alerts, even more, to the importance of assistance services for these individuals.

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Introduction

It is essential to recognize the advances in social assistance policy in recent years and the State's ability to implement social assistance and, above all, the expansion and organization of this policy.

In 2009, the National Social Assistance Council (CNAS) approved Resolution No. 109, of November 11, National Classification of Social Assistance Services, which aims to establish a standardized matrix of social assistance services, organized by level of complexity, with Basic Social Protection and Special Social Protection of medium and high complexity, in addition, it creates minimum parameters for actions and establishes criteria for the quality of services.

Basic and special social protection services are offered at the Social Assistance Reference Centers (CRAS), the Specialized Social Assistance Center (CREAS) and by non-profit social assistance entities, remaining organized as established in the Resolution .

The National Typification of Social Assistance Services, establishes the three services at the level of basic social protection: Service of Protection and Comprehensive Assistance to the Family (PAIF), Service of Coexistence and Strengthening of Links (SCFV) and the Service of Basic Social Protection at Home for people with disabilities and the elderly. ,

purpose of the PAIF is to strengthen the protective function of the family, prevent the rupture of its bonds, promote access and enjoyment of rights and contribute to improving the individual 's quality of life .

The object of the study is related to the SCFV , within the scope of basic protection . It can be noted that the PAIF is executed exclusively by the public authorities in the CRAS , and that this service is the main basic social protection service , and that all other services , at this level of protection , need to be articulated with him.

The Integral Family Protection and Care Service - PAIF consists of social work with families, on an ongoing basis, with the aim of strengthening the protective function of families, preventing the rupture of their bonds, promoting their access and enjoyment of rights and contributing to the improvement of your quality of life. It provides for the development of families' potentialities and acquisitions and the strengthening of family and community ties, through preventive, protective and proactive actions. (BRASIL, 2009, p. 06)

PAIF _ consists of carrying out social work with families, that is, working on needs in order to develop their potential. The main actions developed are: reception , workshops with families, community actions, individualized actions and referrals .

Another service developed by basic social protection is the SCFV, which features a

[...] service carried out in groups, organized based on routes, in order to guarantee progressive acquisitions to its users, according to their life cycle, in order to complement the social work with families and prevent the occurrence of situations of social risk (BRASIL, 2009, p.09).

The Ministry of Social Development and Fight Against Hunger (MDS), 2017, clarifies that the SCFV, in addition to complementing social work with families, is an ongoing service, organized according to the life cycle, aimed at assisting family members who are experiencing situations of vulnerability and/or who have suffered violations by law . From this, it is understood that family and community bonds need to be strengthened and rebuilt , especially in the context of the elderly person.

Given the need to establish actions to assist families, Basic Social Protection must offer PAIF and SCFV from a territorial perspective . This occurs in areas with the highest levels of vulnerability and social risk, being articulated by the n social assistance services , and in the individual 's home territory , which provide opportunities for participation in programs and projects of resident families .

According to Sposati (2013), the concept of territory began to be applied in social and public policies in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s, through the struggle of social movements that demanded that the state take responsibility for compliance of social rights, carried out in close proximity to the assisted population. Still according to the author , it is understood that the territory is not limited to just one area of coverage, but that it contains a historical dimension, building and rebuilding its identity through the dynamics of its social relations. In this way , the application of the presented notion of territory also concerns the need to create links between the institutions that offer public services , their public agents and the user population .

and social policies of these works , as a result of the institutional evaluation of the SCFV of the CRAS da Vila Worker in the municipality of Paranavaí-PR.

The Coexistence and Strengthening of Links service for the Elderly and their Development in the period of the Covid 19 Pandemic

Brazil is undergoing an accelerated demographic transition, which is caused by a growing increase in life expectancy. As a result, this situation demands the planning and implementation of appropriate public policies for this phase of life .

The SCFV takes place from an intervention, being possible and also important , to identify and promote conditions that allow the occurrence of a long and healthy old age, based on the specific public policies existing for this public, such as the National Policy for the Elderly, the Elderly Statute and the National Health Policy for the Elderly. These policies promote actions that seek to improve the quality of life of the elderly .

At the beginning of 2020, with the advent of the global pandemic of Covid 19 , the Coexistence and Strengthening of Links Service , from the CRAS of Vila Operária, starts its activities remotely , through the *WhatsApp application* . During the first two weeks of the Municipal Decree, which stipulates remote work in the municipality, the dynamics of the services offered by CRAS are reorganized . From the reorganization, and the use of the application, the SCFV is kept running, which makes it possible to maintain the strengthening of the bonds between the participants and the CRAS reference team, during the period of the Decree.

It is important to point out that the planning of activities during the pandemic considered the reality of the users served by the CRAS of Vila Operária in the municipality of Paranavaí/PR, and in the trajectory of the execution of the Public Policy of Social Assistance . In this way, the reorganization of the provision of care services sought to overcome the challenges that arose in that period, organizing itself so that individuals were not exposed to vulnerabilities and social risk.

Methodology

The experience report was divided into three stages. The first stage took place through bibliographical and documentary research, the second stage, the collection of information and the third and last stage, the analysis of information.

Minayo (2009) points out that the object of the social sciences is historical , and that the social routine becomes a reflection of its past and the future is based on the determinations already experienced. It is understood , therefore, that society is involved “ in a constant dialectic between what is given and what will be the result of its protagonism” (MINAYO, 2009 , p . 12).

From this perspective, when studying the expectations of elderly women assisted by CRAS in Vila Operária, it is possible to observe the socio-historical aspects they have already experienced, their current problems and their future expectations . Therefore, for the construction of the present work, a qualitative methodological approach was used , considering that it deals with a universe of meanings, values, motives, aspirations, beliefs that cannot be quantified and evaluated based on variables (MINAYO, 2009).

With regard to qualitative research , according to Pádua (1997, p. 31),

[...] qualitative research has been concerned with the meaning of phenomena and social processes, taking into account the motivations, beliefs, values, social representations, which permeate the network of social relationships [...].

The open, structured questions were sent to the effective participants of the SCFV, by the Social Service professional, through the *WhatsApp application* , in the SCFV collective group of CRAS.

The questions were divided into three units, namely: Participation in the Service for Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds, the form of admission and what the result expected by them, based on effective participation. The units were based on three questions, namely: 01. Why are you participating in the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service?; 02. How did you join the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service? How did you start participating ? ; 03. What do you expect from the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service ? .

The percentage of users who had access to the online questionnaire is *equivalent to* about 67% of the group 's participants . For the analysis of the results, only the responses of the elderly women who answered all the questions were selected, that is, 19% .

Data analysis

The aging process of the Brazilian population has been the object of study in different areas of knowledge, represented by the increase in the number of people over 60 years of age. Several studies conclude that this phenomenon is intrinsically linked to the development of the health area, the possibility of treating diseases and improvements in sanitary conditions.

In 2002, however, the disparity between genders at this age was identified, Salgado (2002) , points out that there is “a gender inequality in life expectancy ” , with the greatest being that of women. Women live on average seven years longer than men . However, it is women

who suffer most from the devaluation of the elderly , since there is an intersection between machismo and gerophobia ⁵.

According to data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE),

In 2012, the population aged 60 and over was 25.4 million. The 4.8 million new elderly people in five years correspond to an 18% growth in this age group, which has become increasingly representative in Brazil. Elderly women are a significant majority in this group, with 16.9 million (56% of the elderly), while elderly men are 13.3 million (44% of the group) (PARADELLA, 2018, *online*).

Despite this reality, the SCFV collective is predominantly composed of women, aged between 60 and 90 years, who have participated in activities for more than three years. The construction of the age profile of the users included in the SCFV collective activities and research participants corresponds to 19 people between 30 and 60 years old, 112 people between 61 and 69 years old and 1 person between 90 and 100 years old . Of the total of 132 participants, 111 are female and 21 are male. For this research, only elderly women were selected.

In this perspective, Salgado (2002) points to the problems that arise with the arrival of 60 years and how these affect the female group even more.

The problems or changes that accompany or arise in old age (chronic illnesses, insufficient economic resources, attention or care needs, survival of close friends and family members, among others) are predominantly female problems. On a psychological and social level, women are assigned, in the course of their lives, a series of responsibilities in the family and in society in general, which come with old age and, at these times, are added to it. The woman then faces retirement with minimal or zero income, scarce economic resources, widowhood or separation from the couple, separation from her sons and daughters, care for dependent family members (young or elderly). He also faces feelings of worthlessness, caused by all the socially existing myths and stereotypes. That is: “the non-acceptance of old age”, the denial of their sexuality; “because I am no longer ready for this”; a low self-esteem because: “physically I don't see myself the way I used to”, when social structures require women to be young, beautiful and productive to participate and contribute to society (SALGADO, 2002, p. 10).

However, in the territory of CRAS da Vila Operária, the SCFV aims to contribute to an active, healthy, autonomous aging process, where meetings with elderly people promote family and community coexistence, detecting their needs and motivations, valuing the experience and

⁵Gerophobia is the term used to describe prejudices and stereotypes, in relation to the elderly, based solely on their age (SALGADO, 2002, p.11 *apud* BUTLER; LEWIS; SUDERLAND, 1991).

experiences of each individual. Even during the pandemic, efforts were made to encourage continued participation, and those who reported difficulties with technology and cell phone use were monitored by the technical team.

It is noteworthy that the evaluation process of the service happens continuously . Data collection took place in October and November of 2021 . Still, from the data collection, it was possible to identify that 67% of the users had access to the *WhatsApp application* and the remote service through a *smartphone* .

Eighteen questionnaires were analyzed, which refer to about 19% of the public active in the SCFV. Diverse responses were also considered, since many were the same.

Regarding the first stage: 01. Why are you participating in the Coexistence and Strengthening of Links Service?

“because it is very good to be with more people and learn many good things from activities, we feel happier”.

“I found friends, jobs, teachers . For me , it was a great idea when it appeared, I was very depressed, I had no energy for anything ”.

“because I like the participation, the advice they “ give ” about the age of the elderly, how to prepare, how to do things, from the movies”.

It is verified that from the effective participation there are improvements in the social life. Social Assistance Policy , through the technical guidelines that underlie the work methodologies for the service , guarantees that the elderly have the right to family life, which avoids social isolation . That said, it is concluded that participation in the SCFV is of paramount importance because it strengthens the bonds of solidarity and the feelings of belonging to a collective .

The idea of collective participation also refers to the relevance of territoriality, as discussed by Sposati (2013):

The territory, in this perspective, implies an effort to carry out the apprehension of social relations placed in their space-time and socio-historical context. In this sense, working with the territory category means, at the same time, recognizing its particularity and its possibilities of connection. Another analogy can be made here: the identity of each person is the result of a relational process, since the identification of individuality stems from the connection with others. Thus, it is through the realization of connections that the recognition of the particularity of identity occurs. (SPOSATI, 2013, p. 08)

the second _ step on joining the SCFV: 02. How did you join the Service for Coexistence and Strengthening of Links? How did you start participating ?

“I went to get a CRAS card , and they invited me to the SCFV , I started to participate and I liked it”.

“I suffered from depression, I was undergoing treatment at the CAPS. The most important thing in my life was getting to know the group for the elderly, here we teach the elderly to exercise , I love to exercise , and the courses they have . The coexistence of going out to the cinema , we feel like a child. The way you take care of us . This coexistence is very good”.

“I was well supported by the CRAS coexistence service , you are very nice , I got a lot of colleagues”.

Still according to the technical guidelines that underlie the work methodology, the sports, handicraft and artistic workshops are strategies used to bring people together in groups, with the aim of ensuring spaces for socializing, developing relationships of affection and solidarity. The strategies used allow the development of a work methodology linked to socio-educational work , which, in addition to adding to the development of sociability, also ensures community coexistence.

In the third and final stage, which refers to what is expected from the SCFV: 03. What do you expect from the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service ?

“I hope to relate to other people, learn a lot, because I still have to learn, because we never learned enough, I always have to learn. Anyway, being happier and having contact with other people and that is very good and especially in terms of health and coexistence”.

“I hope the team is always good and understanding, as they always were. They understand and understand the old people . It 's good to be in a group that has the same age as you , the same way of talking, etc. You can interact in a way that makes you feel good and make others feel good , understanding the other's problem without interfering in personal life”.

“I hope the pandemic ends for the group to start again in person. Participate in activities and lectures . I hope that we start to meet and participate in everything as it was before, we miss that participation ”.

From the answers obtained, it appears that there are signs of a situation of vulnerabilities resulting from the pandemic period , as identified “ *we miss this participation* ”, due to the lack of face-to-face participation in the SCFV collective.

It should also be noted that the service performed remotely, attended to the elderly, and also carried out actions to strengthen and maintain the existing bond.

The actions and activities developed by the SCFV seek to stimulate the elderly person's social skills , such as emotion, self-control, courtesy, communication , new social relationships, solutions to conflicts, group tasks , among others . In addition, there is the promotion of experiences to rescue and stimulate the right to learn and experience .

The participation of the elderly person in the planning of activities is very important. The SCFV reference technician, from CRAS da Vila Operária, performs every year, together

with this public, the evaluation of the services provided in that year and also analyzes the suggestions of the elderly, which brings the bond closer and perform the service.

Final considerations

The growing life expectancy is a fact and demands substantial changes in policies aimed at individuals over 60 years of age, that is, the elderly.

The research demonstrates that social coexistence is of paramount importance for the SCFV users, proven through the reports of the present research. Based on the analysis of the collected data, it is clear that the elderly person's feeling of belonging to a group, a service, a certain territory, which aims at coexistence and strengthening bonds, provides new motivations, strengthens respect for the on the other, community and social bonds, and even break through the obstacles of insecurity .

It is noted that the SCFV, offered by CRAS da Vila Operária, in the municipality of Paranavaí/PR, achieves the objective proposed in public policies aimed at the elderly, and provides the population that uses the services with the right to social and community coexistence , strengthening the conviviality.

During the pandemic period, despite the challenges of remote work with the elderly participating in the SCFV, it was possible to maintain strengthened social relationships between the elderly and the CRAS reference team , which in this period. The team sought to reduce the occurrence of situations of vulnerabilities and social risks , a fact that could be aggravated by social isolation . It is noticed through the reports of the elderly women that they are waiting for the return of activities in person, reaffirming the importance of relationships in the collective.

From the interviews, it is identified that the expectations of the elderly, in the effective participation of the SCFV, is the strengthening of the bonds and the conviviality with the other participants, which, provide activities in groups and sociability.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the elderly participants in the research, during the pandemic period, even with the development of SCFV remotely, showed signs of social vulnerability. This fact reaffirms the importance of the service offered and guaranteed by the Law, and even though it is of paramount importance for these individuals.

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APPENDIX 1 - INFORMED CONSENT FORM

This research will be conducted under the responsibility of the Social Service professional at CRAS in Vila Operária, in the municipality of Paranavaí/PR.

Participation implies answering some questions that allow for answers that contribute to the development and result of the research. which will result in the SCFV analysis .

Anonymity is guaranteed, emphasizing that the name or any other personal data that may identify the elderly will not be part of a publication, report or other form of disclosure.

The Social Worker undertakes to systematize information and data within the ethical principles inherent in the scientific research process.

If you agree to participate in this study, type yes in the *whatsApp collective group* .

APPENDIX 2 - SCRIPT OF QUESTIONS - INTERVIEW

Name: _____

Age : _____

Sex: _____

01. Why are you participating in the Coexistence and Strengthening of Links Service?
02. How did you join the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service? How did you start participating ?
03. What do you expect from the Coexistence and Strengthening of Bonds Service ?